
Advantages of Different Views in Tourism

Rasulov Bekzod

Teacher at Uzbekistan Finland Pedagogical Institute

***Annotation.** The logistic activities in the tourism companies contribute to the improvement in the experience and satisfaction of customers, workers, businessmen, suppliers and community, where tourism activity is developed, constituting an effective business management tool, adding value to tourism.*

***Keywords:** transportation, logistic, tourists, roads, travelers.*

INTRODUCTION

The logistics discipline in tourism aims to support the main activities of the sector. In the case of tourism companies, it is about providing services that complement the main activities such as a hotel, whose essential function is to host tourists; a restaurant, whose basic function is to produce food and serve them; a travel agency, provide tourism packages and excursions to attractive places and transport, among other types of companies.

This industry presents the characteristic of being highly sensitive to various variables: it is dependent on the economic, social situation, health crises and natural disasters. Therefore, each activity must be planned in advance, then once it is in development, it is difficult to solve a problem that could be detected in advance.

The relationship between tourism and logistics is basically focused on provisioning, supply and provision activities, activities that are reflected in the transportation of passengers, food, accommodation and material support to tourism programs, being fundamental to consider them when planning and organize a tourist activity or event. The elements of logistics can be organized into a single

system adapted to each event, allowing the order and supply of consumers, products and facilities, seeking to act in favor of the environment, communication and its needs. Tourism activity has three well-defined phases: a beginning, a development and an end. Each of these phases has its particularities, where logistics intervenes in each case in particular.

Both logistics and tourism are based on the same premise: the generation of promises materialized in customer satisfaction, where the service must be at the right time, in the right place and in the right quality. The development of tourism involves understanding and relating both disciplines by the tourist entrepreneur. The deep knowledge of each one of the logistic processes in search of its perfection, culminates in the organizational strategy and in the consequent competitive advantage.

Logistics plays an indispensable role in the tourism industry. Travel and tourism industry closely associate with hospitality sector to provide the total customer solution. Accordingly, passenger transport, cargo transport, warehousing, and creating total tourism product are part and partial of travel and tourism business. The global supply chain is currently faced with huge challenge due to Covid pandemic. Therefore, the future of travel business needs to reshape in line with new normal scenario which is yet to come. This paper explores the timely relevance of explicit application of logistics theories to improve travel and tourism industry to face the current challenges. The conceptual framework introduced in the paper initially identifies the key drivers in customer's destination choice. Thereafter it illustrates the process of transport operation and incorporating hospitality sector through logistics applications to create the tourism product using global supply chain.

The words, travel and tourism are commonly used interchangeably. However, each of these words has specific meanings. Usually, the tourism industry is concerned with people travelling for business or pleasure purposes, staying in their destination for at least one night, and then returning. It refers to travel, but there is a specific purpose in tourism. By contrast, the travel industry has a wider scope, covering more travel purposes and durations. Simply put it, travel refers to the activity of going on a long journey. In commercial perspectives, there is an increasing concern about logistics in tourist services. Logistics is, generally the detailed organization and implementation of a complex operation. Since travel is a highly complex phenomenon, incorporating logistics in travel and tourism operations has a strategic advantage. Improved logistics systems helps to offer refined travel and tourist services. In other words, the business offerings in travel and tourism sector should be able delight its consumers

namely, the tourists, as a comprehensive corporate package. The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) defines tourists as people who "travel to and stay in places outside their usual environment for more than twenty-four (24) hours and not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes not related to the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited". Therefore, integration of logistics enables to derive maximum output that may delight the tourists, using minimum input resources in its processes concerning with travel and tourism activities. If the trip does not include an overnight stay, such person is commonly recognized as a visitor. As defined elsewhere if it includes overnight stay such person may call a tourist.

The study explored the importance of tourism logistics to improve travel and tourism industry. A conceptual framework has been derived based on an opinion survey backed by a comprehensive literature review. Researchers recommend the travel and tourism industry should expand their research beyond supply chain management and explore the advantages of managing supply networks upon establishment of effective and efficient tourism logistics. Since a supply network is developed by connecting multiple supply chains the common delays and pitfalls of a single chain can be avoided. However, since the SN is a new concept derived from the supply chain management it is advisable to conduct further research to ascertain its suitability the context of tourism.

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